

Infrastructuring Critical Data Literacy through Role-playing: a Retrospective Study of the Game ‘Datopolis’

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Organisations require diverse technological infrastructures to create value from data. Because these infrastructures are often haphazardly developed, they cause frictions between the socio-technical agencies of the involved stakeholders. Datopolis is a role-playing game consisting of cards, tiles and tokens that was specifically designed to support such stakeholders to experience, understand and reflect on how data infrastructures should be developed and maintained. Although the game has reached more than 20 organisations in 8 different countries since its original release 8 years ago, little is known about how its resources and rules actually elicit critical reflection among its players. By conducting a retrospective qualitative study consisting of 27 interviews with stakeholders, we uncovered that the prototypical role-playing narrative drives critical reflection through 3 facilitation approaches and 3 play strategies that are anchored in organisational contexts shared among players. We are thus able to present three contributions: 1) a retrospective study grounded in interviews with actual stakeholders being affected by the game; 2) an overview of play strategies and facilitation approaches that enacted the infrastructuring processes through role-play; and 3) critical considerations to operationalise how role-play supports learning, situated in real-world contexts and shaped by facilitation. This study calls for a critical examination of the role of interpretation during learning activities to empower stakeholders in reclaiming control over organisational practices.

CCS Concepts: • **Human-centered computing** → **Collaborative and social computing**; **Empirical studies in collaborative and social computing**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: infrastructuring, critical data literacy, role-playing game, learning, play, metagame, facilitation, retrospective study

1 Introduction

Organisations that seek financial and societal value from generating, collecting, and analysing data depend on socio-technical *infrastructures* [23]. Described as ‘*something that other things “run on”*’ [89], such infrastructures have to be continuously maintained, so they do not break [20]. Infrastructures need to be kept in use so they do not become obsolete [93]; and appropriated, so that they match the abilities of their users [92]. Every action required to keep infrastructures operational belongs to a continuous process conceptualised as ‘*infrastructuring*’ [89]. As infrastructuring tends to happen haphazardly in the background of other ‘*running*’ practices [88], this process is typically taken for granted [8] as it only becomes visible when the infrastructure breaks [91]. As a result,

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Fig. 1. **a.** As players use tokens to claim combinations of data tiles, towers from multiple stacked tokens emerge. These multi-coloured towers visually represent an infrastructure of data tools which players build and maintain through various strategies. By discussing these strategies with the others while they play, players learn about the process of infrastructuring. **b.** All these actions are steered by game resources such as cards, tokens, tiles arranged on the table for a typical play session.

organisations are often compelled to develop workarounds to address urgent issues, which can give rise to unstable working conditions driven by informal and invisible labour performed by their stakeholders [30]. This invisible labour also causes frictions because it requires unevenly distributed long-term commitment from stakeholders [78], who often are not aware of each other's values and practices [65].

Still, by maintaining infrastructures, organisations are able to develop a critical understanding of how socio-technical processes shape their data practices, i.e. data infrastructure literacy [31] and even be able to imagine how these practices can be organised differently [7]. Recent HCI work has used this potential to develop practical learning approaches that unpack the process of infrastructuring. Researchers have revealed that such approaches need to calibrate their activities to the organisation abilities to incorporate learning into their day-to-day practices [2]. When learning revolves around exposing individuals to real-world stakeholder conflicts, it has to support their agency to engage in conflicts according to their own values [42].

We introduce Datopolis, a tabletop game created by the Open Data Institute (the ODI), a UK non-profit organisation active in the data domain, to support critical data literacy among non-experts. The game can be easily accessed either by purchasing a physical copy or by downloading the CC-licensed resources, rules and instructions from GitHub and it does not require any prior knowledge about the topic to be played. Due to its accessibility, it has been played and facilitated on many occasions by individuals and organisations in a variety of circumstances, such as public events, learning workshops and private play sessions.

Datopolis supports up to five players to collaboratively build an artefact consisting of multiple towers of different heights and colours, which together visually represent the data infrastructure of a fictional town. Players build these towers through the actions of drawing cards, connecting tiles and positioning tokens. As they build and negotiate according to roles they act out, players develop strategies that help them maintain the town's wellbeing against damaging events that threaten its people, economy and environment. By role-playing how to build and maintain a data infrastructure, players are able to experience how data practices are shaped by multiple competing socio-technical agencies.

In the 8 years since its public launch, more than one hundred Datopolis play sessions have been held, many of them being facilitated as part of learning activities in over 20 organisations in 8 different countries. Despite its broad outreach, little is known about how the game facilitates learning among players. The goal of this research is to analyse how role-playing the process of infrastructuring towards different outcomes guided by the game's rules and resources supports players to critically reflect on the socio-technical conditions shaping data practices.

We thus report on a retrospective qualitative study with two stakeholder groups - players and facilitators - based on 27 interviews and archival data collected during an internship at the ODI by the first author. First, through 5 exploratory interviews with ODI practitioners combined with archival data made available by the organisation, we gathered information about the development context of Datopolis and subsequent use in learning activities. Next, we conducted 22 interviews using an elicitation protocol which allowed us to recall experiences from former players and facilitators of Datopolis. To analyse the collected data spanning play sessions across many years, we performed a reflective thematic analysis [10] which revealed a wide range of play and facilitation experiences in different organisation settings across sectors.

Our findings reveal that the role-playing actions of building and maintaining the data infrastructure drive critical reflections as they are initiated by player strategies, triggered by facilitator approaches, while also being anchored in real-world examples of organisational practices. Informed by game and learning theory, we discuss how players develop their own critical understanding of a data infrastructure while physically building it and how all the decisions made about and during role-play influence the players reflective process of discussing their actions with the other players.

We summarise the contributions of this work for designers and facilitators of game-based learning activities for critical data literacy as: 1) a retrospective qualitative study grounded in interviews with the original and new stakeholders of Datopolis; 2) an overview of play strategies and facilitation approaches developed in parallel with play, in the context of real-world data practices; and 3) a set of critical considerations to guide the operationalisation of role-play to support learning, while also being situated in the real-world and influenced by decisions from facilitators. With these contributions, this study calls for a critical examination of the role of interpretation during play to empower stakeholders in reclaiming control over organisational practices.

2 Related work

2.1 Infrastructuring as developing critical data literacy

2.1.1 Infrastructuring. The concept of *infrastructure* foregrounds the 'taken-for-granted material and organisational substrate of human action' [51] which consists of technological artefacts that mediate human relations and activities at a global scale [35]. It was first conceptualised by Science and Technology (STS) scholars [8, 88, 90, 91] to challenge the view of technologies as isolated artefacts by analysing instead the relations created as technologies become embedded into 'a background' of socio-technical structures [88]. These structures are invisible to anyone using them [8], unless there is a moment of 'breakdown' which brings them forward until they are up and 'running' again [91].

From this relational perspective, Computer-Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW) and Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) scholars have emphasised that information infrastructures do not work in perpetuity once installed to support human activity. Instead, infrastructures require ongoing maintenance [102], repair [29] or patch-working [64]. These responsibilities do not only include technological tasks, but activities that maintain social and institutional relations [55], by exploring community values [37], by reimagining working conditions [39] or by developing opportunistic strategies [103]. While the underlying infrastructure may not be immediately visible, the associated

maintenance activities are rarely one-off efforts. Rather, they represent sustained and complex collaborations among multiple stakeholders. These stakeholders learn from one another as they share knowledge internally [6], extending it to the organisations and communities they engage with [98]. Additionally, this knowledge is distributed over time, aligned with the timing of required interventions [48].

2.1.2 Critical Data Literacy. This relational, situated and distributed view of infrastructures is useful to help stakeholders to critically understand how social, political and cultural aspects shape their data practices such as data production, sharing, or analysis [31]. As critical scholarship has previously emphasised, data is never ‘raw’, but it is imbued with the perspectives of those who analysed it [21], the methods and tools used to produce it [1], and is embedded in the local geographies where it was produced [59].

Building on these socio-technical aspects that shape data, the concept of *critical data literacy* refers to the abilities that allow stakeholders to use and produce data in a critical way [101]. By emphasising criticality, data literacy does not only build technical skills so that data can be used as a resource to extract value from [57]. Rather, it cultivates a critical understanding of the context where data is created and the decisions that govern data transformation and circulation [31]. Pangrazio and Selwyn have proposed an actionable framework comprising five progressive levels of critique [68]. The first level involves *identifying* diverse data types, while the second focuses on *understanding* their origins and varied applications. The third level, *reflexivity*, enables recognition of the implications of data for oneself and others. The fourth level develops *strategies* for effective data utilisation, and the fifth employs *tactics* to resist and challenge systems of privilege and oppression. In this research we will focus on how playing Datopolis fosters *reflexivity* about the context where data is produced and used, while developing *strategies* to create new applications based on data.

2.1.3 Infrastructuring approaches for critical data literacy. Previous CSCW and HCI infrastructuring approaches have targeted critical skills by using toolkits (e.g.[2, 85, 86]) to stimulate reflection on data ethics and accountability; by organising data analysis workshops as part of long-term literacy programs (e.g.[22, 42, 70]), aiming to invite organisations to scrutinise the context where data is produced and to use data to challenge systemic inequality.

One such approach is Bitacora [2], a toolkit consisting of a web interface for social media data analysis and an accompanying worksheet that introduces breaks for reflection while performing data analysis tasks. From testing Bitacora with a non-profit organisation, researchers have learned that *reflexivity* should be supported by facilitators in specific learning activities, rather than interrupting more high-stakes ones. However, stand-alone toolkits used by facilitators are not sufficient to support critical reflection, because social support and physical materials are also required to adapt the toolkit to the context of the data practices it aims to improve [84]. When card-based toolkits are used for guiding classroom deliberations among students, relying on the toolkit alone leads to over-scripting the collaborative discussions which disrupts learning [85]. Moreover, the complex technical jargon used by such toolkits does not allow practitioners to contextualise the terminologies into their own practices [86].

By combining multiple activities with a low participation barrier for non-experts such as storytelling, visualisation and role-playing, workshops are able to help non-profit organisations to identify the protocols, practices and politics they need to develop so they can use data to highlight their own advocacy [70]. For example, the Reimagining Work project combines interviews with local activists, a board game and prototyping to help social and economic justice organisations reflect about the politics of infrastructures and reimagine the relation between labour and technology [26]. Still, if the context of their practices does not support criticality and is not open for

reconfiguration, then practitioners are unable to further apply the critical skills gained in these workshops [42]. Furthermore, to support practitioners to build a critical consciousness, this context should allow them to refuse engaging in data practices that do not align with their values because, for example, the dataset they need to analyse promotes racist perspectives [22]. Compared to these approaches, Datopolis offers a tangible, game-based toolkit that enables stakeholders to simulate and explore scenarios drawn from their own organisational data practices through collaborative and facilitated play.

2.2 Collaborative learning through games

2.2.1 Game theory for learning. Games are proven effective learning tools [19] because they have been shown to increase player motivation [28] through immersive [40], enjoyable activities [106], that allow players to build confidence in their own skills [16]. Games support cognitive, behavioural, affective, and sociocultural engagement with complex topics [76] by allowing players to devise solutions to problems [82], to collaborate with their peers [105] and to select topics according to their preferences [72]. Games are effective behaviour change tools [5] because they model desirable behaviours [24] in locations and contexts where players can easily adopt these behaviours [25].

Games engage players in an artificial conflict defined by rules and enacted through resources (such as cards, boards, dice, and tokens), resulting in a quantifiable outcome of winning or losing [97]. Because this artificial conflict is inspired by real-world actions [28], players learn by being able to experience these actions within a condensed frame of time and space [75]. Game rules clearly separate actions performed while playing from the real world, according to the ‘game-player-world’ model theorised by Jesper Juul [45]. This structure creates a risk-free space where players can safely practice and refine skills before using them in real-world scenarios [99]. By planning their actions based on their personal interpretations of the game rules, players create strategies [104] to adapt to novelty and solve problems [27].

In role-playing games, play strategies are further guided by roles that players take on [9], which give players the ability to explore otherwise inaccessible identities [34]. Players gradually develop identities during play by creating narratives and expressing perceptions about the other identities in the game [100]. Once player perceptions are being woven into role-playing narratives, players develop a metagame i.e. ‘the relationship between the game and outside elements, including everything from player attitudes and play styles to social reputations and social contexts in which the game is played’ [97]. The metagame facilitates ‘retelling play’ [97], enabling players to articulate their in-game strategies in relation to personal objectives beyond the game. This process allows players to rehearse skills acquired during play in real-world contexts [46]. Moreover, as players alternate between playing and retelling, they engage in metacommunication, explicitly signalling whether they are within the game world or the real world [81]. This metacommunication supports collaborative, iterative meaning-making through shared narratives [44].

2.2.2 Games designed for collaborative learning. Leveraging their immersive, situated and collaborative affordances, games have been used by the CSCW and HCI communities to support collaborative learning on topics spanning from health [50] including dementia [62], autism [13], menstruation [58], disability [61] or recovery [38]; sustainability [95, 111] including food waste [87], plastic recycling [53], or sustainable development trade-offs [3]; to language literacy [11], storytelling [54] and musical composition [56]; and technology literacy including on smart city technologies [94], computational literacy [73] and privacy and security [63] and cybersecurity [96].

Among digital games, online games have been preferred as they allowed players to interact with others anonymously, which helped them go past embarrassment when learning a new skill, but it also increased their reliance on accurate visual representation of other players [80].

Interactive PC and console games have allowed players to experience the human immune system when role-playing body cells fighting viruses inside the human body [107]. Existing entertainment games have been repurposed for their potential for teaching interactive data visualisation, however the interactive aspects distracted players from the information communicated [49].

Tangible games support learning by allowing for multisensory experiences and co-located interactions between multiple players. For example, FeastyMaze is a tangible game that uses visual, tactile, olfactory and auditory riddles to cultivate awareness of a balanced diet among preschoolers, which have to be well-balanced to not overload children cognitively [12]. Goopy Gut Trail is a board game that supports tangible interaction among co-located players who come together to learn about how microbes influence their gut health by reflecting on their own behaviour [69]. Climate Club is a role-playing card game that helps players to make sense of climate actions by discussing unsustainable everyday behaviour and brainstorming solutions to improve it, which sometimes confused players as to whether they were discussing their own lives or the game scenarios [83]. Several games also required a facilitator in order to control the pace of the learning activity in the classroom, where school children were taught about their traces online [47] or while playing tangible tabletop games where players are trained to fend off cybersecurity attacks [33].

While many collaborative learning games are designed for formal education environments and tested with school children and university students, there is a growing interest among scientists and non-profit organisations to create games to support adults in becoming more critical about democratic and social issues. For example, GuesSync! is an online chat-based game that reduces political hostility by randomly matching players with opposite views to discuss politics, which sometimes leads to players resisting to engage with others when they feel triggered [79]. Fakey leverages player suspicion towards questionable behaviour by priming against misinformation they interact with a fake social media feed, which improves their news literacy [66]. Unlike prior studies that evaluated game experiences only during or immediately after play, our retrospective research investigates how stakeholders playing Datopolis, often across multiple sessions over several years, developed and sustained critical reflections on the data infrastructures they were building in their own practices.

3 Datopolis

Between 2014 and 2016, the ODI developed Datopolis through an iterative design process to promote the ODI mission of communicating the benefits of open data to organisations and society at large. In doing so, Datopolis enables non-experts to experience infrastructuring in a relatable, inclusive and collaborative manner.

3.1 Iterative design process

Design decisions were guided by three temporal constraints to accommodate organisations with limited time. Firstly, the set-up had to occupy only minutes, prompting the use of cards, tiles and tokens that could be deployed immediately or assigned at random. Secondly, gameplay was confined to 45–60 minutes, so the winning conditions were tied to a predetermined cap on the number of tokens each player could place. Thirdly, to facilitate deeper engagement, the game offered three distinct outcome pathways, each aligned with a different level of conceptual complexity.

The first prototype underwent internal and informal evaluation across three play sessions to assess how players understood the game content and interpreted the rules. Based on these observations, a second iteration was tested by members of government and civil society at various civic-tech events and summits hosted by the ODI. Feedback after each session led the design team to introduce two changes in the final production version.

Fig. 2. The *Tools*, *Roles* and *Events* outcomes are achieved by following rules conveyed by game resources such as tool cards, event cards and role cards. A detailed description of how resources and rules guide the three outcomes is given in Appendix B. Figure created by the authors using original images from game resources licensed under the CC-BY copyright by the ODI.

First, because the binary opening or closing of data tiles oversimplified the real-world spectrum of shared data by only allowing players to open or close data tiles, role cards with distinct agendas were added to require players to negotiate before opening data. Second, to emphasise collaborative infrastructuring, a collective victory condition was introduced while preserving individual agency via role-based strategies.

3.2 Role-playing Datopolis

Gameplay relies on two elements: resources, physical components such as cards, tokens and the town dashboard, and rules, provided on the cards and in an instruction manual. The combination of game resources, together with the rules needed to play them, summarised in Figure 2 and described in Appendix B, form the metaphor of building a data infrastructure.

The data infrastructure exemplified in Figure 1 is built as players place tokens on different types of data tiles to claim ownership of an application built on that data. As multicoloured towers of varying heights emerge, players score points under three possible outcomes:

- Tools - one or several players win by being the first to place 10 tokens;
- Roles - one or several players win if their unique role achieved its purpose;
- Events - all players win if the town wellbeing reaches its maximum, or all lose if the town suffers irreparable damage.

The Tools outcome can stand alone as a simplified version of the game. The Roles and Events outcomes build on this foundation, encouraging progressively deeper competitive and collaborative interactions. The following paragraphs describe how role-play unfolds under each outcome.

3.2.1 Tools. To win the *Tools* outcome, players must be the first to stack ten **tokens** in the data infrastructure towers. They do so by building tools according to **tool cards**, which illustrate the specific combinations and positions of **data tiles** required. Because only open **data tiles** may be used, players must request that opponents open any closed tiles they need. Once all required **data tiles** are open and correctly positioned, a **token** is placed on each tile used. Over successive rounds, these multicoloured stacks grow into towers that physically represent the coordinated actions of choosing, placing, combining and stacking, necessary to construct the data infrastructure.

3.2.2 Roles. Each player assumes a secret role drawn at the start of the game, introducing distinct agendas that motivate their actions. To secure victory under the *Roles* outcome, a player must

fulfil the objectives specified on their **role card**, revealing their role only when claiming success. Throughout play, these agendas guide decisions about which tools and **data tiles** to prioritise.

3.2.3 Events. The *Events* outcome introduces unpredictable negative occurrences via **event cards**, each of which threatens the town wellbeing. To prevail, players must collaborate, occasionally subordinating or revising their individual agendas, to build tools and combine **data tiles** that bolster infrastructure against these threats. After resolving each event, they update the **town dashboard** by moving the **dashboard markers** to reflect the current status of the town.

4 Methodology

We conducted a retrospective qualitative study to be able to analyse past experiences of stakeholders who played the game over a duration of 8 years. The data collection consisted of two phases, an *exploratory* phase to understand the game and identify organisations playing it, and a *protocol-based* phase targeting more in-depth accounts from present and past players. This study was approved by the first author's university ethics commission.

4.1 Exploratory data collection

When the first author joined the the ODI team, she had minimal prior knowledge of Datopolis. To remedy this, she conducted an initial series of exploratory interviews with the game regular facilitators and organised a play-test session. These interviews were partly audio recorded, due to the confidential information that was discussed in some instances, for example information about the organisations that requested the game as a service of the ODI. Where audio recording was not suitable, the first author took notes which were later improved after validation and feedback by the interviewees, complemented by notes taken during several alignment meetings with the ODI co-authors. At the same time, although not captured in a scientific manner, water-cooler conversations prompted by a copy of Datopolis strategically placed on the first author's desk helped to trigger recollections of past experiences and play tactics from colleagues who had played the game. Concurrently, the ODI team provided archival data on game design and production, offering quantitative insights into the game impact since launch. Through several collaborative meetings, analysis of these materials helped us refine the research question.

4.2 Protocol-based data collection

Learning from the exploratory interviews that the game is typically played with some form of facilitation, we treated players and facilitators as two distinct stakeholder groups. Since we aimed to collect qualitative accounts of playing and facilitating Datopolis from stakeholders whose experiences were dispersed over a span of several years and who represented different organisations, we designed a data collection protocol to ensure consistency. A big part of the play experiences relies on players visually analysing towers of multiple heights and colours, combination which resembles a physical visualisation of a bar chart. Therefore, we were inspired to structure the interview by the elicitation technique used by Hogan, Hinrichs and Hornecker [36] in Data Visualisation research. This technique gathers in a guided and systematic way detailed and accurate accounts of data visualisation interpretations. We based our protocol on three steps from the elicitation technique [36]: *introduction*, *evocation* and *retrieval*.

4.2.1 Introduction. We collected background information, such as their experience with playing Datopolis, the current work domain, role and seniority. We also introduced the interview protocol, obtained consent for recording, and addressed any questions the interviewees might have had.

4.2.2 Evocation. Interviewees were shown an anonymised archival photograph of a Datopolis session, in which the table, game components and surrounding environment remained visible but all player faces were obscured. Using this image as a visual aid, we posed a series of structured questions designed to gauge their recall of the game rules, resources and outcomes. To elicit personal insights, we then asked each interviewee to imagine themselves as one of the players in the photograph and describe how they would have acted in that scenario.

4.2.3 Retrieval. We built on the previous step to ask them to recall their own experiences. We kept the visual support as we asked interviewees to share how they played, the strategies that they and the other players used and the topics that were discussed during play. Because sessions often occurred within organisational learning contexts, we also asked interviewees to describe the context in which the game was played as part of their work.

Since facilitators and players experience the game differently, we asked facilitators to compare two play sessions with different players, at different stages during play and varying physical conditions. As 3 interviewees explained that they first played the game at a the ODI summit and then after learning the rules, they facilitated sessions with colleagues in their organisation, we adapted the protocol on the spot to elicit both facilitator and player experiences from them. All interviews were conducted online by the first author and they were audio and screen recorded. We used a Miro board (available in Appendix C) to share the questions and the visual support with the interviewees.

4.3 Recruitment

We recruited 24 stakeholders through a combination of snowball sampling and social-media outreach. Initially, three ODI facilitators referred twelve stakeholders from organisations in their network who had played or facilitated the game within the previous year. To include longer-term experiences, we then contacted two individuals who had shared sessions dating back to 2018; they in turn recommended two additional stakeholders. Finally, we posted an advertisement on social media, which yielded two more respondents. As these latter individuals had not yet played Datopolis but intended to purchase it, the two interviews were treated as exploratory and excluded from the main protocol.

This strategy gave us the ability to access stakeholders from different organisations across all sectors, in a variety of domains, in roles with many seniority levels. At the same time, our online interview approach allowed us to conduct interviews regardless of the geographical location or time-zone of our stakeholders, and yielded responses from the UK, New Zealand, Canada, Switzerland, South Africa. We proceeded with the protocol-based data collection with a final cohort of 22 stakeholders from 8 different organisations including the ODI, equally divided among facilitators and players, as illustrated in Table 1.

4.4 Data analysis

Because the first author was simultaneously embedded within the ODI and committed to maintaining analytical distance, we adopted a reflexive thematic analysis approach [10]. We aimed to reach a coding approach that is *'collaborative and reflexive, designed to develop a richer, more nuanced reading of the data, rather than seeking a consensus on meaning'* (P:584). The first author led the coding of 25 hours of verbatim-transcribed audio-video recordings. We thematised our codes after discussing with the co-authors while the analysis process was informed by our interest in tracing the critical reflections through game and learning theory. We combined the thematic analysis of interviews with content analysis of archival data to fill in gaps in understanding the initial design goals of Datopolis and how they were currently interpreted by the stakeholder groups using the

game. Whenever archival records proved insufficient, the first author sought clarifications from ODI colleagues. Furthermore, during the writing process, some of the findings needed to be further aligned with the ODI colleagues, both stakeholders of this study and co-authors, as our method brought forth insights which required additional validation and reprocessing.

5 Results

#	Pseudonym	Player	# Played	Facilitator	# Facilitated	Experience (y)	Role	Seniority	Sector
1	Abigail	x	1			>1	data analyst	mid	private
2	James	x	6-10	x	2-5	4	software engineer	mid	public
3	Marjorie	x	1			>1	data analyst	mid	private
4	Tim	x	1			>1	data ethicist	mid-senior	public
5	Cornelia	x	1			>1	data privacy protection	mid-senior	public
6	Taylor	x	2-5			2	data policy lead	senior	private
7	Peter	x	11-20	x	6-10	8	open data expert	senior	public
8	Marcus	x	2-5			1	data governance expert	senior	public
9	Betty	x	1			>1	data governance expert	mid-senior	private
10	Alison	x	6-10			8	data governance expert	senior	public
11	Will	x	11-20	x	11-21	4	data governance expert	senior	public
12	Sophia			x	2-5	4	data transformation	mid	non-profit
13	John			x	20-30	8	data skills consultant	mid-senior	private
14	Dorothea			x	2-5	2	data governance expert	mid-senior	public
15	Eddie	x	6-10	x	2-5	8	data licensing and IP rights	mid-senior	public
16	Archer			x	6-10	4	data governance expert	mid	private
17	Steven			x	11-20	8	data governance expert	senior	non-profit
18	Clara			x	2-5	1	data governance expert	mid	non-profit
19	Samuel			x	6-10	2	data governance expert	mid	non-profit
20	Chloe	x	2-5			8	data innovation expert	mid-senior	non-profit
21	Charlie						open data expert	mid-senior	public
22	Liam						data transformation	mid-senior	non-profit

Table 1. The 22 stakeholders from the public, private and non-profit sectors held various roles and seniority levels in their organisations, all with different years of experience of playing Datopolis. We used pseudonyms instead of their real-world names.

We interviewed 22 stakeholders from various roles and seniority levels in organisations belonging to different sectors, as presented in Table 1. Stakeholder engagement with Datopolis ranged from a single play session to regular play over several years, including some who facilitated sessions within their organisations. Based on their experiences, we generated 67 codes grouped in 11 sub-themes and 3 themes that describe how stakeholders - as players and facilitators - appropriated the game resources, rules and outcomes according to their diverse learning needs and organisation learning agendas, as summarised in Figure 3.

5.1 Facilitation approaches - steering play towards learning agendas.

Most (19/22, n=22) of the play sessions in which stakeholders engaged were not spontaneous; rather, they were structured and directed by facilitators. Only 3/22 stakeholders - Alison, Peter and Abigail - reported that they did not have a facilitator for their play sessions. Yet, even in their case, they remember how one experienced player took the lead in facilitating their group when they felt stuck, for example by reading the rules out loud. When facilitators guided the play, they reportedly 'changed the rules', according to Dorothea, aiming to steer the group discussions towards learning agendas agreed previously with the organisations that hosted the play session. In this way, facilitators developed specific approaches, which we grouped under *Operational model*, *Extreme scenario*, and *Contained hazard* and represented in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. We mapped the results onto the game - play - world model [45] which describes the game, the player’s relation to the game and the relation between playing and the rest of the world. The metagame develops in parallel with play, combining metagaming discussions about play strategies with examples of data practices from the real-world. With dotted, interrupted and continuous arrows we represented actions belonging to facilitators, players and the game that connect the game, play and real-world.

5.1.1 *Operational model.* The first decision that facilitators make when preparing a play is choosing one of the three game outcomes that best fits the learning agenda of the organisation whose members are playing. The learning agenda depends on whether these organisations are part of the public or private sector, according to Steven, and whether they approach data infrastructures either from a ‘strategic perspective’ or an ‘operational perspective’, according to Will. According to his explanation, a strategic perspective steers the data infrastructure long-term evolution and sets priorities, whereas an operational perspective keeps the infrastructure running day-to-day by developing and maintaining it.

Because most organisations described in our study wanted to learn about data infrastructures from an operational perspective, all 11 facilitators interviewed reported choosing the *Tools* outcome in most plays they remembered facilitating. By playing towards this outcome, the play actions focused on physically building tools by manipulating game resources, effectively modelling the iterative process of building infrastructures at an operational level. Players confirmed that the tangible game resources were ‘so visually appealing’, according to Clara, that they allowed players to make the connection between the metaphor of the game and real life data practices by ‘sparking conversation’ (John).

To be sure that they could steer play at an operational level, facilitators preset game resources so that only data tiles and tool cards were in play. By removing role cards and sometimes even event cards, they avoided complicating the play with additional roles such as scientists, non-profits or businesses. In this way, facilitators believed they will steer away players from acting at a strategic level, from diverse competing interests. Dorothea explained how this approach allowed the stack of tokens to get ‘a little bit higher’, maximising the visual contrasts between the data tiles that were reused multiple times to build tools with, and the tiles that were more difficult to approach.

However, even though players were collaboratively building the same shared data infrastructure, they still perceived roles differently. This occurred even when a simplified version of the game was in play, without role cards assigned individually to players. Player perceptions varied with

the tools built and the parts of the infrastructure maintained, effectively creating different roles according to the resources at hand. Samuel explains why perceptions varied:

'All of the data mainly gets used in the middle, so there's always like a central kind of orchestration point and then you see all the little bits start to get tagged onto the edges. You've got all the big players, the people who can really utilise that data and do cool stuff with it, and then you get all the kind of specialist stuff coming off the edges.'
(Samuel)

5.1.2 Extreme scenario. In the few cases where both operational with strategic learning agendas were prioritised, facilitators (Steven, Sophia and Samuel) reported combining the *Roles* and *Events* outcomes. The complexity introduced by these outcomes allowed facilitators to train specific players, before play began, towards open or closed data scenarios, so that they could covertly influence the outcomes at the table towards a completely open or a closed data infrastructure. According to facilitators, playing in such an extreme scenario, which would hardly be possible in real-world data practices, allowed players to experience the consequences of their infrastructuring actions such as not being able to build a health app when all health data is closed, in a rapid and contrasting way.

This approach was often based on assigning players specific roles, revealed at the end of play, during a plenary discussion. Here, facilitators reflected how the 'differences in the game' (Sophia) demonstrated how one stakeholder opening or closing datasets influenced the entire infrastructure built. As a result, players 'got very competitive' (Samuel) as they were lead into an extreme scenario of infrastructuring where the data infrastructure would consists of an abnormally high amount of towers, or the opposite, only very few towers being built. To skew the play even more towards the extreme, these players would also receive preset resources such as 'tool cards which are easy to build', allowing them to build more applications with data than they were normally able to, according to Steven:

'Certain players were instructed to play a strategy which no one knows, but it guarantees us an outcome in the game. So we plant someone who makes sure that it all goes open, they make everything open. But they can't let on that they're doing that deliberately.'
(Steven)

5.1.3 Contained hazard. Oppositely, several facilitators (Clara, Peter, Archer, John) reported pre-setting a different amount or type of event cards than recommended by the game rules. Their aim was to limit the damage inflicted by cards to the town infrastructure. By preventing an early town collapse, the game let players progress through multiple rounds and carry out far more infrastructure building and maintenance actions. This approach reportedly allowed players to reflect about infrastructure breakdown based on 'factors outside of your control' (Clara). Similarly, several facilitators curated specific event cards that players could draw, thus limiting the gravity of the threats to the fictional town's infrastructure so as to avoid 'going into crisis a third time' (Peter).

Facilitators sometimes softened the impact of event-card hazards on the town dashboard, keeping the game alive for at least one extra round and giving players more time to explore the infrastructuring process at their own pace. Archer explains his approach:

'I think the one of the minor things that I changed is, and again this depends on the audience and how I wanna calibrate the game for difficulty, is that I will sometimes allow them to credit the dashboard with more than one metric on the cards. So in other words, if environmental impact or social impact are both highlighted, I allow them to lift both items because you can always offset that with ad hoc events or disasters and that brings the dashboards down again.' (Archer).

However, some facilitators chose not to interfere with the event cards to allow players to experience infrastructure breakdown through the metaphor of the town collapse, as John motivates:

'If they're gonna kill the town, let them kill the town and learn the lesson'. (John)

5.2 Play strategies - appropriating rules and resources.

Both players (11/22) and facilitators (11/22) noted that, although the session was bounded by formal rules, resources, and facilitation styles, the iterative, competitive, and cooperative character of the game only emerged through the continuous appropriation of those constraints by players. Players kept planning how to build or maintain towers, adjusting their strategies in real time in response to actions of other players, randomly drawn cards, and their own intuition. We describe the appropriation process in relation to 3 play strategies: *Building*, *Competition* and *Cooperation*, represented in Figure 3.

5.2.1 Building. It was agreed among the players we interviewed that the iterative process of positioning and connecting physical tiles and tokens allowed players to 'experience what it takes to build a data infrastructure', as emphasised by John. As players combined tiles representing data types such as transport or democratic to build towers of stacked tokens representing services such as apps, products or research, they were able to visually grasp the multiple steps required to build an infrastructure that would otherwise 'take years' (John) in the real-world. This visual interpretation, according to James, allowed players to associate a physical tower with 'a graph or a bar chart' from multiple stacked tokens.

However, taking part in this iterative process was only the first step. Because the number of data tiles available were rarely enough to build new tools on their, players needed to plan their actions in a similar way as stakeholders plan infrastructuring actions in the real-world. First, players needed to scan the data tiles 'that you could see in front of you' (Alison). From all the combinations available, players proceeded to find suitable ones from the tool cards available, as recalled by Betty who would 'take a new card and see if there was anything to build off there'. Once the tiles needed were located within that round of play, players proceeded to make combinations according to the 'the patterns on the card' (Marjorie).

Sometimes, just as with real-world infrastructures, there were not enough resources available to build applications. Here, players needed to be flexible enough by finding 'ways to swap' tool cards with other players. If this was yet not possible during the time allocated within their round, the alternative would have been to 'wait and hope' for a better allocation during next rounds (Marcus). After multiple rounds, it became clear that success relied on player ability to appropriate the game resources to their advantage, by identifying the 'opportunities on the board for them' (Tim). Additionally, player success also depended on the ability to respond to other play strategies, by using resources already shared by others. Realising that building a data infrastructure required a big amount of fore-planning created frustration among some players, as revealed by Cornelia:

'It took us a while to build the infrastructure and I think a source of frustration was that data sharing required a lot of infrastructure [building] that we hadn't really thought about'. (Cornelia)

5.2.2 Competition. During the first rounds, players developed new tools by combining data tiles that were open for everyone to built on. However, as play advanced, they realised that many of the tiles that seemed available were actually closed by other players. This required players to verbally convince the owners of the closed tiles to open, in exchange for opening another tile of their own. In several cases, these negotiations failed, prompting players to convince someone else, which would end up with 'another person pop up and start offering' (Taylor). These negotiations resembled

the real-world infrastructuring process of developing social relations among stakeholders with competing interests. Just like in real-world negotiations, players were driven by specific agendas depending on roles assigned at the beginning of play. These roles were interpreted as back-stories to their actions, allowing players to ‘look at open data from different angles’ (James). Eddie describes this process:

‘If we’re in the private sector, what are our parameters? The private sector might need to make revenue and avoid giving away secrets. They relate to the role cards in the game, but definitely they constructed themselves specifically. By doing that, it initiated a conversation about how these different groups interact with each other.’ (Eddie)

In several cases the negotiations for data tiles became very heated, as players decided to ‘hold [data] tiles closed’ (Tim) to prevent others from building so they could ‘win the game’ (Marcus). This resulted in players trying to find every ‘opportunity to block somebody’ (Marcus), which even went as far as blocking the entire infrastructure for the rest of the game. The infrastructure that resulted had an abnormally small number of ‘towers built for the amount of data’, as Peter describes. In these moments, facilitators intervened by asking reflective questions to help players understand how in the real-world, infrastructuring actions ‘happen outside of your control and [make you] adapt’ (Tim).

5.2.3 Cooperation. Apart from adapting to competing strategies, players also adapted to unpredictable events that ‘lowered the town dashboard’ (Taylor) during each round. Because the magnitude of these events requested players to collaborate with others, players reportedly reflected on how in the real-world, they too had to find unusual allies in sectors that ‘you may not think’ (Marcus) are suitable for working together. According to Eddie, developing relations between stakeholders that do not necessarily have the same values illustrates the reality of ‘data sharing as [a] slightly chaotic’ process. If players were able to find common ground among multiple competing values players were rewarded, according to Clara, with a data infrastructure where ‘you could really physically see the difference’ of multiple players ‘building together’ (Taylor) to achieve shared goals. Furthermore, players explained what actions they took to reveal values through cooperative strategies, as explained by Betty:

‘I would be encouraging everyone to be as open as possible because by being open you can collaborate better.’ (Betty)

However, not all players considered that facing unpredictable events during play was enough to simulate real-world circumstances of a data practice, since ‘not everybody will want to cooperate out in the real-world like in our play’ (Tim). As a result, the game reportedly created ‘a little feeling of unreality’ (Tim).

5.3 Metagame - merging play and facilitation through critical discussion.

Both players (11/22) and facilitators (11/22) recalled that players constantly discussed with each other about their play strategies during play, thus engaging in metagaming, as represented in Figure 3. In these discussions, they often connected their play strategies to real-world organisational work practices they took part in, while grounding decisions in personal values and interests. As such, the connection between play and real-world during metagame discussions had two different directions: starting from play strategies and relating them to real-world practice examples; or starting by sharing a real-world experience that can apply to a play strategy in the game. James describes how the metagame discussions were perceived as being even more valuable than playing the game:

‘Rather than me learning the mechanics of open data from the game, it was more about us helping others get the idea, I think.’ (James)

5.3.1 Discussing play strategies in relation to real-world practices. Most frequently, metagame discussions started as players verbally described their strategies by mapping out their next move, for the entire table to hear and verbally react to, because they wanted others to consider the ‘stakes involved in sharing [data]’ (Cornelia). This allowed players to develop a ‘conversation around the game’ (James) by interpreting the hypothetical town whose infrastructure they were maintaining. As players wanted to motivate their strategies to other players, they discussed practices from their own organisations, such as ‘making sure that new data sets are captured and registered’ (Marcus), or having ‘clients in different sectors, some in highly regulated ones and others in ones not regulated at all’ (Cornelia).

To ensure that the discussions were relevant to all players, in the context of the learning agendas set before the game, facilitators ‘would pop in to check in on’ players (Cornelia). Their approaches varied, from taking an ‘observational role’ (Steven) which allowed players to steer discussions, to more hands-on approaches. For example, several facilitators recalled interfering with play by prompting players to explain their strategies such as ‘a negotiation over a piece of data’ (Samuel). Some of these questions included ‘What was the purpose?’, ‘Who did it first?’ and ‘Why did you do it?’ (Eddie). The stronger type of facilitator intervention during play is described by Samuel, sharing that he aimed to ‘elevate’ the reflections by ‘pushing the conversation as far as [he] can get it’ (Samuel).

5.3.2 Discussing real-world practices in relation to play strategies. As metagame discussions became increasingly complex after each turn, players ended up motivating their real-world decisions with predetermined agendas that they role-played. This type of metagame discussion started from the opposite side compared to the previous one - from a real-world example that relates to play, rather than explaining a play strategy through a real-world practical example.

This practice allowed players to reflect on the social infrastructure required for opening data. For example, Betty explained how she would ‘just kept buying open’ because this is ‘who she is’ even though this made it ‘very difficult to negotiate’ because she had nothing to bargain for with the other players. On the flip-side, some of the players who were asked to open their data tiles had concerns about ‘the proprietary nature of data’ (Cornelia), since typically ‘competitors get insights to use in competition’ (Cornelia).

In response, some players expressed frustration when others closed data sets, and this frustration was fuelled not by playing the game, but by real-world data practices where ‘all are out for themselves’, thus making infrastructuring ‘very irritating as a data governance manager’ (Betty). As Betty exemplifies, players used real-world experiences to reflect about the play strategies of fellow players:

‘It depends on your personal ethics, right? Whether you’re a giver or taker, and whether you’re happy to collaborate or not, so that person who’s not showing their hand is not very collaborative and strikes me as someone who’s more strategic’. (Betty)

These reflections were not solely steered by players, but had guidance from facilitators who asked questions such as ‘How did it make you feel? How does that affect you as an organisation?’ (Steven), or provided additional instructions in order to gather ‘introspective kind of feedback’ (Samuel) that would keep the discussions flowing according to their facilitation approach. Dorothea explained how as a facilitator, her ‘intent was to work together’, therefore she was constantly on the look-out for player strategies that were ‘helping or hindering the others’. However, even with facilitation, there were moments during play when discussions would derail outside of the learning agendas, because the strategies would be ‘played out and then a topic started to fall out of that’ (James).

6 Discussion

Our results show how playing Datopolis supports the development of critical literacy around infrastructuring by first allowing players to experience the process of building a data infrastructure, then supporting them to relate this process to their real-world data infrastructures, all under the guidance of experienced facilitators. As such, we offer a methodological contribution to applying critical data literacy theory [68] in a facilitated, game-based context involving data-oriented organisations. We bring evidence that developing critical data literacy is a process that happens gradually, by first understanding data in a personal and organisational context and then by applying the learned strategies to one's own data practices.

Yet, our results also indicate that the development of critical data literacy through facilitated, game-based learning is contingent upon a set of conditions that extend beyond the game design itself. These conditions emerge from the dynamic interplay between game, players, and facilitators. In examining these factors, we propose a series of recommendations aimed at operationalising the design and implementation of learning activities that are situated, facilitative, and grounded in a practical context.

6.1 Operationalising metagame discussions to support situated learning.

According to our results, learning activities supported through metagame discussions are situated within a personal context, defined by player interpretations of data infrastructures; a social context, where multiple players discuss, negotiate and compete against each other for game resources; and a practical context defined by organisational practices experienced by players in their work, and constantly related to the game metaphor of a town infrastructure. These contexts interact with each other dynamically as play unfolds, influencing the critical reflections developed by players both individually and collaboratively.

6.1.1 Personal context. Our findings show that when one player verbally explains a personal interpretation, other players struggle to form interpretations independently.

As players appropriated game rules and resources according to their existing knowledge of maintaining data infrastructures over time (see 5.2.1 Building), personal interpretations emerged regarding how to apply this knowledge to the town's data infrastructure (see 5.3 Metagame). These interpretations evolved iteratively, beginning with physical gestures directed towards data tiles, and later shifting to verbal explanations of new maintenance strategies related to their stacked towers. However, the metagame discussions revealed that hearing other players verbally describe their maintenance strategies directly influenced individual interpretations (see 5.3 Metagame). Interviewed players described adapting their strategies in response to these verbal exchanges, particularly during competitive play (see 5.2.2 Competition). Our findings expand previous work that found that reflections within collaborative game-based activities are often shaped by dominant voices of players who take the lead in discussions [77]. This tendency can be perhaps explained by how spoken reflections enable players to enrich their interpretations through storytelling [18] and through adapting the metaphorical learning content to individual learning needs [4].

Considering these aspects, we recommend that:

R1. To mitigate dominant perspectives that suppress individual player interpretations during group discussions, games that rely on personal reflections for learning should combine collaborative and individual activities, perhaps by alternating individual with collaborative rounds. This approach requires precise turn-taking instructions delivered either through written cards or verbally enforced by facilitators.

6.1.2 Social context. According to our evidence, while the metagame discussions allow players to collaboratively develop play strategies, these discussions do not remain aligned with the learning agendas.

The players we interviewed reported developing strategies (see 5.2 Play Strategies) not only by relying on their personal interpretations, but also by engaging in metagame discussions with the other players (see 5.3 Metagame). Though dynamic dialogue, players collaboratively developed strategies by combining their individual interpretations of the town data infrastructure with the shared interpretations of other players. This dialogue allowed players to experience play as social interaction, since they ended up not only discussing about the game (see 5.3 Metagame), but also about their personal knowledge and experiences. Previous studies have found that social interactions during play allows players to sustain the knowledge and skills they acquired over time [52], by adding contextual knowledge from lived experience to the theoretical knowledge provided by the game [67]. Moreover, discussions support learning through peer-to-peer feedback [74], while in a game context they enhance player sense of belonging to the group [46]. However, our findings suggest that very often the dialogue between players digresses towards topics that are not part of the game metaphor. As a result, they undermine the learning agendas set by facilitators together with their own organisation. This behaviour can be perhaps explained by how metagame discussions seamlessly blend real-world experiences with the game metaphor as players constantly relate play strategies to their own practices outside of the game [81]. For this reason, we recommend that:

R2. To ensure that learning agendas are followed throughout play, collaborative discussions between players should not diverge too far or too often from the game metaphor. This can be achieved through a game setup that limits discussions time per round, effectively steering players to move to a different topic. Another approach could be through facilitation strategies that bind discussions closer to play strategies with questions and verbal instructions.

6.1.3 Practical context. Our results indicate that metagame discussions allow players to share practical knowledge, although it is often unclear to players whether this knowledge originates from the game metaphor or from the real-world context.

As players shared concrete examples of data infrastructuring from their experience, they abstracted these examples back into strategies of building and maintaining hypothetical data infrastructures in the game context (see 5.2 Play strategies). This approach did not only situate play in the personal and shared interpretations of the players, but also in the practical knowledge about infrastructuring accumulated from real-world practices they were part of (see 5.3 Metagame). However, during metagame discussions players did not purposefully switch between play and real-world. Rather, discussions flowed continuously from hypothetical to real infrastructuring examples during each play round. As a consequence, players were not critically aware of the difference between learning content and personal anecdotes which manifested as several players not being able to explain the reasoning behind developing a certain play strategy. This could be explained by the documented fluid structure of metagame discussions which unfold organically without players being aware whether the discussion is situated inside or outside play [46]. More generally, learners have been shown to develop personal scenarios that help them to generalise experiences into knowledge they can later use in their practices [14]. Regarding these aspects, we recommend that:

R3. Learning through games should allow players to purposefully relate the learning content to practical experience. Facilitation approaches should include questions and remarks during play that invite players to reflect on their strategies; game resources should include a reflection round between play rounds, while instructions on cards and game board should nudge players to relate game resources to their equivalent in the real world.

6.2 Operationalising learning agendas to support facilitated learning.

According to the players and facilitators we interviewed, facilitators of game-based learning introduce constraints that frame the learning process in accordance to predefined learning agendas both before play and during play.

6.2.1 Framing learning before play. Our results indicate that facilitators frame play within learning agendas that players are not fully aware of.

As presented in (see 5.1 Facilitation approaches), in order to fulfil the learning agendas set by the organisations where the game was played, facilitators framed metagame discussions (see 5.3 Metagame) even before play started, by for example adapting game rules or predefining game resources. According to previous studies on peer-driven learning, such calibrations are part of the scaffolding actions of facilitators that offer gradual support during the learning activity, thus adapting to individual needs [15]. Also, this support creates a collaborative and ongoing reflection process between facilitators and players needed for delivering learning content [43]. Yet, according to our interviews, players were not aware of these calibrations before entering play, even though they were part of the organisations responsible for how the play was framed. By not being fully aware of the context where their critical reflections are developing, players cannot meaningfully position their own interpretations within the larger practices of their organisation. Previous studies have found that positioning learning in a wider context allows the development of a critical understanding of how to apply the knowledge learned in real-world data practices [22]. The lack of critical positioning was partially avoided as facilitators did indeed divulge their approach to the players after play ended, specifically to create a collaborative learning moment. Their approach inspired us to propose the following recommendation:

R4. Facilitated game-based learning should consider a transparent means of teasing out the learning agendas by supporting a collaborative round-by-round game commentary after play ends, perhaps even combined with a shared reflection about implications to the real-world practices.

6.2.2 Framing learning during play. According to our results, when facilitators steer play strategies and discussions towards learning agendas, players develop a limited understanding of their strategies.

As facilitators continuously intervened during metagaming, they steered discussions towards learning agendas, especially when they observed that players strayed too far (see 5.3 Metagame). Sometimes they did so by verbally adding new examples from real-world practices; by supporting discussions with reflective questions; or even by planting a trained player to nudge the others towards potentially learning opportunities (see 5.1.2 Extreme scenario). This approach is perhaps explained by how facilitated learning activities need to provide continuous instructions that adapt the learning content to the organic nature of collaborative discussions between peers [15]. However, while in collaborative learning such interventions have promised to improve the quality

of discussions [41], and in game based learning interventions help players to integrate the new knowledge with prior one [110], providing too much support inhibited players from developing their own interpretations in the long term. Our results thus contribute further evidence to previous studies that found that if players are not aware of the learning agendas pursued by the facilitators, they are unable to critically position themselves in relation to the learning content [60]. Moreover, we extend previous work that has revealed the importance of unmediated interaction with the game rules for developing critical skills [17]. Considering these aspects, we recommend that:

R5. Facilitated game-based learning should develop learning agendas collaboratively with players, by for example inviting players to take turns facilitating the game play. This would still allow facilitators to intervene when needed, yet provide players the agency to choose the topics they want to discuss more elaborately.

6.3 Operationalising practical knowledge to improve the impact of learning through play.

Interviews conducted after stakeholders played the game as part of a learning activity supported by their work organisation suggest that playing the game without also integrating real-world infrastructuring practices creates mismatches between what players learn from a hypothetical play context and the actual practices they encounter in their work.

6.3.1 Hypothetical play context. Our findings show that the metagame discussions taking place during play do not straightforwardly lead to critical reflections about infrastructuring data practices from the real-world.

Players reportedly developed strategies (see 5.2 Play Strategies) to entice others into competitive play actions (see 5.2.2 Competition) such as blocking other player ability to extend their data services into new domains because they wanted to entice their real-world work colleague (according to Taylor). As a result of this approach, the metagaming discussions were not always based on genuine learning interests, but were driven by the motivations such as having fun or impressing others (see also 5.3 Metagame), which did not lead to meaningful reflections about infrastructuring data practices. This can be potentially explained by the fact that players perceive learning through play as a risk-free and hypothetical playground for testing new skills [99]. Our results extend prior findings that role-playing games let players explore otherwise inaccessible scenarios [34], as evidenced by our metagame discussions. However, these hypothetical debates rarely catalyse real organisational change, since they stop short of prompting players to transfer insights back into their actual practices [109]. Therefore, we recommend that:

R6. To foster learning through games, post-game debriefs should be integrated as an additional learning activity, so to connect hypothetical discussions with real-world practices [25]. For instance, players might describe to colleagues how they would transfer play strategies to real-world stakeholder collaboration, as an example of infrastructuring from their own work.

6.3.2 Mismatches with real-world practices. According to our results, when critical insights are developed during play, they seldom translate into concrete day-to-day infrastructuring practices.

Several components of Datopolis allowed players to reflect critically about infrastructuring aspects: the hypothetical town’s data infrastructure (see 5.2.1 Building); the collaborative play strategies interpretation (see 5.2.2 Competition, 5.2.3 Cooperation); and the similarity between

these strategies and the real-world strategies players experienced in their own practices (see 5.3 Metagame). However, the reflections did not immediately lead to actions outside of the hypothetical play context, as discussed in Section 6.3.1. According to our interviews, once play ended, players were unable to directly apply what they learned into their own practices. From a game perspective, perhaps this can be explained by how metagame discussions, even when they reach a reflective level, they are still self-referential rather than pointing to experiences outside of the game, because metagaming is expected to keep players cognitively and motivationally engaged in play [108]. From a critical learning perspective, this lack of transformative action reflects back on the wider conditions in most organisations where developing one's critical approach to infrastructuring data does not always align with the day-to-day realities of data work [42].

Our game-based findings contribute to the evidence that initiatives designed to foster critical data literacy act as infrastructures for skill development [22]. But to make those skills matter, the initiatives themselves must be woven into the social, technical, and cultural settings where skills will be applied [32]. One such approach could be that learning initiatives start from the existing knowledge within their target communities, so individuals gain genuine ownership of the learning outcomes [71].

Considering these aspects, we make the following recommendation:

R7. Learning activities should be embedded in the broader organisational and social context where the newly acquired critical skills can be applied, refined, and revisited. This integration sets the stage for constructive follow-up such as group discussions or peer-to-peer feedback when skills cannot be directly applied to a real-world work context.

7 Limitations and reflection on method

7.1 Recruiting stakeholders from the ODIs's network

Because we recruited stakeholders through snowball sampling, our interviewees came from organisations closely connected to the ODI, and we recognise that this proximity may have influenced their accounts. We managed this limitation by expanding recruitment to social media channels while also asking stakeholders to recommend potential new leads. Moreover, as the stakeholders we contacted had left the organisations where they first played Datopolis, we encountered many dead-ends. While we could not reach 10 potential stakeholders because of expired contact information, we were able to still interview 4 who agreed to contribute their retrospective accounts. The elicitation protocol was useful for evoking their past play sessions because it used the comparison to the session they were asked to analyse as an entry point to their own recollections.

7.2 Retelling play

As stakeholders recollected their Datopolis play sessions, they began to recall play strategies and facilitation approaches developed while playing by relating these to the play session analysed. While they verbally narrated their own play actions, stakeholders used the visual support of the elicitation protocol to anchor their own experiences. By doing this, stakeholders engaged in metagaming years after their own session has ended, only this time they took full control over their play session, by recalling it from their own perspective. However, because these recollections happened many years after the original play sessions, they often lacked details which made it difficult later on to analyse thematically. Particularly regarding metagaming, as stakeholders remembered discussions they had during metagaming, it was sometimes not clear during the interviews whether the explanations they gave have been discussed during play or represented interpretations of a past experience at the

time of the interviews. To overcome this limitation, we asked for clarifications during interviews, and where we were still not sure, we discussed within the team of co-authors the best theme placement for those coded explanations.

8 Conclusion

By conducting a retrospective qualitative study with the original and new stakeholders of the game ‘Datopolis’, we analysed how playing the game is able to support players to experience, understand and become critically aware of the process of infrastructuring. The game was first created by a non-profit to help its own network understand the complex socio-technical work behind using and maintaining open data. In the eight years since its launch, roughly twenty other organisations have adopted it for purposes that far exceed the original goals set for the game.

Our results showed that facilitators used 3 different approaches - operational model, extreme scenario and contained hazard - to achieve different outcomes, while players developed 3 different strategies - building, competition and cooperation - which they interpreted in the context of their real-world practices during discussions that occurred in parallel with play.

We discussed these findings in relation to literature about learning games and collaborative and social learning, allowing us to present seven recommendations for using games for developing critical reflections. Our recommendations suggest to consider how learning through play is situated in a personal, social and practical context; to consider how facilitation may constrain reflections throughout the learning process; to widen the impact of game-based learning by coupling it with other learning activities and by infrastructuring the learning process into real-world practices.

From this perspective, we call for a critical examination of the role of metagaming for allowing players to reclaim power over their play experience; and of the power of facilitation to steer and limit player reflections. In the context of play sessions conducted by organisations, metagaming with colleagues might be able to help players to gain influence over the culture and practices in their own organisations.

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References

- [1] AKBABA, D., KLEIN, L., AND MEYER, M. Entanglements for visualization: Changing research outcomes through feminist theory. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* (2024).
- [2] ALVARADO GARCIA, A., WONG-VILLACRES, M., HERNÁNDEZ, B., AND LE DANTEC, C. A. Bitacora: A toolkit for supporting nonprofits to critically reflect on social media data use. In *Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (2024), pp. 1–29.
- [3] ANTLE, A. N., WARREN, J. L., MAY, A., FAN, M., AND WISE, A. F. Emergent dialogue: eliciting values during children’s collaboration with a tabletop game for change. In *Proceedings of the 2014 Conference on Interaction Design and Children* (New York, NY, USA, 2014), IDC ’14, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 37–46.

- [4] ANVARI, S. S., HAMMER, J., AND WEHBE, R. R. "more than just a game, it's an app that builds awareness around mental health": Mental health stigma reduction using games for change. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 8, CHI PLAY (Oct. 2024).
- [5] BARANOWSKI, T., BUDAY, R., THOMPSON, D. I., AND BARANOWSKI, J. Playing for real: video games and stories for health-related behavior change. *American journal of preventive medicine* 34, 1 (2008), 74–82.
- [6] BØDKER, S., DINDLER, C., AND IVERSEN, O. S. Tying knots: Participatory infrastructuring at work. *Computer Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW)* 26 (2017), 245–273.
- [7] BOWKER, G. C. *Information infrastructure (s): Boundaries, ecologies, multiplicity*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2014, ch. The infrastructural imagination.
- [8] BOWKER, G. C., AND STAR, S. L. *Sorting things out: Classification and its consequences*. MIT press, Cambridge, MA, 1999.
- [9] BOWMAN, S. L. *The Functions of Role-Playing Games: How Participants Create Community, Solve Problems and Explore Identity*. McFarland, Jefferson, NC, 2010.
- [10] BRAUN, V., AND CLARKE, V. Reflecting on reflexive thematic analysis. *Qualitative research in sport, exercise and health* 11, 4 (2019), 589–597.
- [11] CAI, M., REBOLLEDO MENDEZ, G., AREVALO, G., TANG, S. S., ABDULLAH, Y. A., AND DEMMANS EPP, C. Toward supporting adaptation: Exploring affect's role in cognitive load when using a literacy game. In *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, 2024), CHI '24, Association for Computing Machinery.
- [12] CAI, X., JIN, K., SHI, S., HUANG, S., HUANG, O., WANG, X., CHENG, J., LIN, W., YAO, J., HU, Y., ZHANG, C., AND YAO, C. "see, hear, touch, smell, and...eat!": Helping children self-improve their food literacy and eating behavior through a tangible multi-sensory puzzle game. In *Proceedings of the 23rd Annual ACM Interaction Design and Children Conference* (New York, NY, USA, 2024), IDC '24, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 270–281.
- [13] CARLIER, S., VAN DER PAELT, S., ONGENAE, F., DE BACKERE, F., AND DE TURCK, F. Using a serious game to reduce stress and anxiety in children with autism spectrum disorder. In *Proceedings of the 13th EAI International Conference on Pervasive Computing Technologies for Healthcare* (New York, NY, USA, 2019), PervasiveHealth'19, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 452–461.
- [14] CARROLL, J. M. *Making use: scenario-based design of human-computer interactions*. MIT press, 2003.
- [15] CERNA, K., MÜLLER, C., RANDALL, D., AND HUNKER, M. Situated scaffolding for sustainable participatory design: Learning online with older adults. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 6, GROUP (Jan. 2022).
- [16] CONSTANT, T., AND LEVIEUX, G. Dynamic difficulty adjustment impact on players' confidence. In *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems* (2019), pp. 1–12.
- [17] CUTTING, J., AND IACOVIDES, I. Learning by doing: Intrinsic integration directs attention to increase learning in games. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 6, CHI PLAY (Oct. 2022).
- [18] DANILOVIC, S., CHEE, K., AND SKOP, M. Playful resilience: Empowering recovery through autobiographical game-based storytelling in the opioid epidemic. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 8, CHI PLAY (Oct. 2024).
- [19] DE FREITAS, S. Are games effective learning tools? a review of educational games. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society* 21, 2 (2018), 74–84.
- [20] DENIS, J., MONGILI, A., AND PONTILLE, D. Maintenance & repair in science and technology studies. *Tecnoscienza—Italian Journal of Science & Technology Studies* 6, 2 (2015), 5–15.
- [21] D'IGNAZIO, C., AND KLEIN, L. F. *Data feminism*. MIT press, 2023.
- [22] DISALVO, C., ROTHSCHILD, A., SCHENCK, L. L., SHAPIRO, B. R., AND DISALVO, B. When workers want to say no: A view into critical consciousness and workplace democracy in data work. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 8, CSCW1 (Apr. 2024).
- [23] ELSDEN, C., SYMONS, K., BUNDUCHI, R., SPEED, C., AND VINES, J. Sorting out valuation in the charity shop: Designing for data-driven innovation through value translation. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 3, CSCW (nov 2019).
- [24] FERNÁNDEZ GALEOTE, D., AND HAMARI, J. Game-based climate change engagement: Analyzing the potential of entertainment and serious games. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 5, CHI PLAY (Oct. 2021).
- [25] FERNÁNDEZ GALEOTE, D., LEGAKI, N.-Z., AND HAMARI, J. From traditional to game-based learning of climate change: A media comparison experiment. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction* 7, CHI PLAY (2023), 503–525.
- [26] FORLANO, L. E., AND HALPERN, M. K. Speculative histories, just futures: From counterfactual artifacts to counterfactual actions. *ACM Trans. Comput.-Hum. Interact.* 30, 2 (Apr. 2023).
- [27] FUDENBERG, D., AND LEVINE, D. K. *The Theory of Learning in Games*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, 1998.
- [28] GARRIS, R., AHLERS, R., AND DRISKELL, J. E. Games, motivation, and learning: A research and practice model. *Simulation & gaming* 33, 4 (2002), 441–467.
- [29] GARRISON, P., JANG, E. H. B., LITHGOW, M. A., AND PACE, N. A. "the network is an excuse": Hardware maintenance supporting community. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction* 5, CSCW2 (2021), 1–20.

- [30] GOFF, M., HODGSON, D., BAILEY, S., BRESNEN, M., ELVEY, R., AND CHECKLAND, K. Ambiguous workarounds in policy piloting in the nhs: tensions, trade-offs and legacies of organisational change projects. *New Technology, Work and Employment* 36, 1 (2021), 17–43.
- [31] GRAY, J., GERLITZ, C., AND BOUNEGRU, L. Data infrastructure literacy. *Big Data & Society* 5, 2 (2018), 2053951718786316.
- [32] GUI, X., LI, Y., AND WU, Y. Teacher-guardian collaboration for emergency remote learning in the covid-19 crisis. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 5, CSCW2 (Oct. 2021).
- [33] HAFNER, L., WUTZ, F., PÖHN, D., AND HOMMEL, W. Tasep: A collaborative social engineering tabletop role-playing game to prevent successful social engineering attacks. In *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security* (New York, NY, USA, 2023), ARES '23, Association for Computing Machinery.
- [34] HAMMER, J., TO, A., SCHRIER, K., BOWMAN, S. L., AND KAUFMAN, G. Learning and role-playing games. In *Role-playing game studies*. Routledge, 2018, pp. 283–299.
- [35] HARVEY, P., JENSEN, C. B., AND MORITA, A. Introduction: infrastructural complications. In *Infrastructures and social complexity*. Routledge, 2016, pp. 19–40.
- [36] HOGAN, T., HINRICH, U., AND HORNECKER, E. The elicitation interview technique: Capturing people's experiences of data representations. *IEEE transactions on visualization and computer graphics* 22, 12 (2015), 2579–2593.
- [37] HOUSTON, L., JACKSON, S. J., ROSNER, D. K., AHMED, S. I., YOUNG, M., AND KANG, L. Values in repair. In *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems* (2016), pp. 1403–1414.
- [38] HYMES, K., HAMMER, J., SEYALIOGLU, H., DOW-RICHARDS, C., BROWN, D., HAMBRIDGE, T., VENTRICE, J., BAKER, M., KIM, Y. J., HUTCHINGS, T., AND EVANS, W. S. Designing game-based rehabilitation experiences for people with aphasia. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 5, CHI PLAY (Oct. 2021).
- [39] IRANI, L. C., AND SILBERMAN, M. S. Stories we tell about labor: Turkopticon and the trouble with" design". In *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems* (2016), pp. 4573–4586.
- [40] JENNETT, C., COX, A. L., CAIRNS, P., DHOPAREE, S., EPPS, A., TIJS, T., AND WALTON, A. Measuring and defining the experience of immersion in games. *International journal of human-computer studies* 66, 9 (2008), 641–661.
- [41] JEONG, H., AND HMELO-SILVER, C. E. Seven affordances of computer-supported collaborative learning: How to support collaborative learning? how can technologies help? *Educational Psychologist* 51, 2 (2016), 247–265.
- [42] JOHNSON, B., RYDAL SHAPIRO, B., DISALVO, B., ROTHSCHILD, A., AND DISALVO, C. Exploring approaches to data literacy through a critical race theory perspective. In *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (2021), pp. 1–15.
- [43] JOHRI, A., AND YANG, S. Scaffolded help for learning: How experts collaboratively support newcomer participation in online communities. In *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Communities and Technologies* (2017), pp. 149–158.
- [44] JORGENSEN, J., AND STEIER, F. Frames, framing, and designed conversational processes: Lessons from the world café. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science* 49, 3 (2013), 388–405.
- [45] JUUL, J. *Half-real: Video games between real rules and fictional worlds*. MIT press, 2011.
- [46] KAHILA, J., VALTONEN, T., LÓPEZ-PERNAS, S., SAQR, M., VARTIAINEN, H., KAHILA, S., AND TEDRE, M. A typology of metagamers: identifying player types based on beyond the game activities. *Games and Culture* (2023), 15554120231187758.
- [47] KAHILA, J., VARTIAINEN, H., ARKKO, E., LIN, A., POPE, N., AND TEDRE, M. Enhancing understanding of data traces and profiling among k–9 students through an interactive classroom game. In *Proceedings of the 19th WiPSCE Conference on Primary and Secondary Computing Education Research* (New York, NY, USA, 2024), WiPSCE '24, Association for Computing Machinery.
- [48] KARASTI, H. Infrastructuring in participatory design. In *Proceedings of the 13th Participatory Design Conference: Research Papers-Volume 1* (2014), pp. 141–150.
- [49] KEJSTOVA, M., STASTNA, T., AND KRIGLSTEIN, S. Play and viz: Using entertainment games for exploring data visualizations. In *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on the Foundations of Digital Games* (New York, NY, USA, 2024), FDG '24, Association for Computing Machinery.
- [50] KIM, Y., BHATTACHARYA, A., KIENZT, J. A., AND LEE, J. H. "it should be a game for fun, not exercise": Tensions in designing health-related features for pokémon go. In *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, 2020), CHI '20, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 1–13.
- [51] KORN, M., REISSMANN, W., RÖHL, T., AND SITTLER, D. Infrastructuring publics: A research perspective. *Infrastructuring Publics* (2019), 11–47.
- [52] KOU, Y., AND GRAY, C. M. Supporting distributed critique through interpretation and sense-making in an online creative community. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 1, CSCW (Dec. 2017).
- [53] LAKSMI, M. P., AND ARDI, R. Serious simulation gaming as learning media for plastic waste recycling management system in indonesia: A conceptual model. In *Proceedings of the 3rd Asia Pacific Conference on Research in Industrial and Systems Engineering* (New York, NY, USA, 2020), APCORISE '20, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 187–192.

- [54] LEE, C., AND MINDEL, J. R. Closer and closer worlds: Using llms to surface personal stories in world-building conversation games. In *Companion Publication of the 2024 ACM Designing Interactive Systems Conference* (New York, NY, USA, 2024), DIS '24 Companion, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 289–293.
- [55] LEE, C. P., DOURISH, P., AND MARK, G. The human infrastructure of cyberinfrastructure. In *Proceedings of the 2006 20th anniversary conference on Computer supported cooperative work* (2006), pp. 483–492.
- [56] LEE, J., CHO, H., AND KIM, Y. Bean academy: A music composition game for beginners with vocal query transcription. In *Extended Abstracts of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, 2023), CHI EA '23, Association for Computing Machinery.
- [57] LETOUZÉ, E., BHARGAVA, R., DEAHL, E., AND SANGOKOYA, D. Beyond data literacy: Reinventing community engagement and empowerment in the age of data. Tech. rep., Data-Pop Alliance, New York, NY, 2015. Accessed: 15 June 2018.
- [58] LIANG, X., ZHANG, J., MA, J., YAO, J., LIN, W., ZHU, Z., MA, Y., YING, F., YAO, C., ZHOU, L., HANSEN, P., ZHAO, Y., AND WANG, G. Menstrual monster: A tangible interactive co-educational game designed for teenagers. In *Extended Abstracts of the 2022 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, 2022), CHI EA '22, Association for Computing Machinery.
- [59] LOUKISSAS, Y. A. *All data are local: Thinking critically in a data-driven society*. MIT press, 2019.
- [60] LOWY, R., MAGIAWALA, K., MITTAL, S., HALL, K., ROBERTS, J., AND KIM, J. G. Research-education partnerships: A co-design classroom for college students with intellectual and developmental disabilities. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 8, CSCW2 (Nov. 2024).
- [61] LUNA, S. M., XU, J., PAPANGELIS, K., TIGWELL, G. W., LALONE, N., SAKER, M., CHAMBERLAIN, A., LAATO, S., DUNHAM, J., AND WANG, Y. Communication, collaboration, and coordination in a co-located shared augmented reality game: Perspectives from deaf and hard of hearing people. In *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, 2024), CHI '24, Association for Computing Machinery.
- [62] MAKRI, M., AND TSOLAKI, M. Innovative serious games for people with dementia developed through intergenerational interventions.: The “bridge” project: A european innovative approach. In *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments* (New York, NY, USA, 2022), PETRA '22, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 678–682.
- [63] MAQSOOD, S., AND CHIASSON, S. Design, development, and evaluation of a cybersecurity, privacy, and digital literacy game for tweens. *ACM Trans. Priv. Secur.* 24, 4 (Sept. 2021).
- [64] MCCLEARN, J., JENSEN, R. B., AND TALHOUK, R. Security patchworking in lebanon: Infrastructuring across failing infrastructures. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction* 8, CSCW1 (2024), 1–26.
- [65] MENG, A., DISALVO, C., AND ZEGURA, E. Collaborative data work towards a caring democracy. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 3, CSCW (Nov. 2019).
- [66] MICALLEF, N., AVRAM, M., MENCZER, F., AND PATIL, S. Fakey: A game intervention to improve news literacy on social media. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction* 5, CSCW1 (2021), 1–27.
- [67] ORR, J. E. Narratives at work: story telling as cooperative diagnostic activity. In *Proceedings of the 1986 ACM Conference on Computer-Supported Cooperative Work* (New York, NY, USA, 1986), CSCW '86, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 62–72.
- [68] PANGRAZIO, L., AND SELWYN, N. *Critical Data Literacies: Rethinking Data and Everyday Life*. MIT Press, 2023.
- [69] PASUMARTHY, N., PATIBANDA, R., LING, Y., VAN DEN HOVEN, E., DANAHER, J., AND KHOT, R. A. Goopy gut trail: Board game play to understand human-microbial interactions. *Proc. ACM Hum. Comput. Interact.* 6, CHI (2022), 1–31.
- [70] PEER, F., AND DISALVO, C. Workshops as boundary objects for data infrastructure literacy and design. In *Proceedings of the 2019 on designing interactive systems conference* (2019), pp. 1363–1375.
- [71] PEER, F., AND DISALVO, C. The work of infrastructural bricoleurs in building civic data dashboards. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 6, CSCW1 (Apr. 2022).
- [72] PEIRCE, N., CONLAN, O., AND WADE, V. Adaptive educational games: Providing non-invasive personalised learning experiences. In *2008 second IEEE international conference on digital game and intelligent toy enhanced learning* (2008), IEEE, pp. 28–35.
- [73] PELLICONE, A., LYONS, L., KUMAR, V., ZHANG, E., AND BERLAND, M. Rainbow agents: A collaborative game for computational literacy. In *Extended Abstracts of the Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play Companion Extended Abstracts* (New York, NY, USA, 2019), CHI PLAY '19 Extended Abstracts, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 597–604.
- [74] PIHLAINEN, K., KORJONEN-KUUSIPURO, K., AND KÄRNÄ, E. Perceived benefits from non-formal digital training sessions in later life: views of older adult learners, peer tutors, and teachers. *International journal of lifelong education* 40, 2 (2021), 155–169.
- [75] PIVEC, M. Play and learn: potentials of game-based learning, 2007.
- [76] PLASS, J. L., HOMER, B. D., AND KINZER, C. K. Foundations of game-based learning. *Educational psychologist* 50, 4 (2015), 258–283.

- [77] POELLER, S., BAUMANN, N., AND MANDRYK, R. L. Power play: How the need to empower or overpower other players predicts preferences in league of legends. In *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, 2020), CHI '20, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 1–13.
- [78] PROST, S., VLACHOKYRIAKOS, V., MIDGLEY, J., HERON, G., MEZIAN, K., AND CRIVELLARO, C. Infrastructuring food democracy: The formation of a local food hub in the context of socio-economic deprivation. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 3, CSCW (Nov. 2019).
- [79] RAJADESINGAN, A., CHOO, D., ZHANG, J., INAKAGE, M., BUDAK, C., AND RESNICK, P. Guessync!: An online casual game to reduce affective polarization. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 7, CSCW2 (Oct. 2023).
- [80] RANKIN, Y. A., TIBI, S., KENNINGTON, C., AND HAN, N.-E. In-game social interactions to facilitate esl students' morphological awareness, language and literacy skills. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 5, CHI PLAY (Oct. 2021).
- [81] SALEN, K., AND ZIMMERMAN, E. Games as the play of simulation. In *Anthropology of the Arts*, G. Bakke and M. Peterson, Eds. Routledge, New York, NY, 2017.
- [82] SANCHO, P., MORENO-GER, P., FUENTES-FERNÁNDEZ, R., AND FERNÁNDEZ-MANJÓN, B. Adaptive role playing games: An immersive approach for problem based learning. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society* 12, 4 (2009), 110–124.
- [83] SANDBHOR, P., AND HOOK, J. Climate club: A group-based game to support sensemaking of climate actions. In *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on the Foundations of Digital Games* (2024), pp. 1–12.
- [84] SCHEEPMAKER, L., KENDER, K., FRAUENBERGER, C., AND FITZPATRICK, G. Leaving the field: Designing a socio-material toolkit for teachers to continue to design technology with children. In *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on human Factors in computing systems* (2021), pp. 1–14.
- [85] SHEN, H., DENG, W. H., CHATTOPADHYAY, A., WU, Z. S., WANG, X., AND ZHU, H. Value cards: An educational toolkit for teaching social impacts of machine learning through deliberation. In *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency* (New York, NY, USA, 2021), ACM, pp. 850–861.
- [86] SHEN, H., WANG, L., DENG, W. H., BRUSSE, C., VELGERSDIJK, R., AND ZHU, H. The model card authoring toolkit: Toward community-centered, deliberation-driven ai design. In *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency* (2022), pp. 440–451.
- [87] SINCLEAR, D., BIRCH FLENSBOG, L., LINDBLAD FOGSGAARD, A., AND LOCHTEFELD, M. Face-the-waste-learning about food waste through a serious game. In *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Multimedia* (2021), pp. 67–72.
- [88] STAR, S. L. The ethnography of infrastructure. *American behavioral scientist* 43, 3 (1999), 377–391.
- [89] STAR, S. L., AND BOWKER, G. C. How to infrastructure. *Handbook of new media: Social shaping and social consequences of ICTs* (2006), 230–245.
- [90] STAR, S. L., AND RUHLER, K. 20 steps toward an ecology of infrastructure: Design and access for large information spaces. *Boundary Objects and Beyond: Working with Leigh Star* (2016), 377.
- [91] STAR, S. L., AND STRAUSS, A. Layers of silence, arenas of voice: The ecology of visible and invisible work. *Computer supported cooperative work (CSCW)* 8 (1999), 9–30.
- [92] STINE, K., AND VOLMAR, A. Infrastructures of time: An introduction to hardwired temporalities. *Media infrastructures and the politics of digital time: Essays on hardwired temporalities* (2021), 9–38.
- [93] STOCK, R. Broken elevators, temporalities of breakdown, and open data: how wheelchair mobility, social media activism and situated knowledge negotiate public transport systems. *Mobilities* 18, 1 (2023), 132–147.
- [94] STOKES, B., ARROYO, H., LOEWEN, M., STEVENSON, T., AND KARR, C. J. A playful city in the cards: Sharing power in game design by extending the card metaphor. In *Extended Abstracts of the 2020 Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play* (New York, NY, USA, 2020), CHI PLAY '20, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 375–378.
- [95] TAGHIKHAH, F., RAFFE, W. L., MITRI, G., DU TOIT, S., VOINOV, A., AND GARCIA, J. A. Last island: Exploring transitions to sustainable futures through play. In *Proceedings of the Australasian Computer Science Week Multiconference* (2019), pp. 1–7.
- [96] TAREQUE, M. H., DEUTEKOM, S., ANVIK, J., AND BASHIR, M. You hacked my program! teaching cybersecurity using game-based learning. In *Proceedings of the 26th Western Canadian Conference on Computing Education* (New York, NY, USA, 2024), WCCCE '24, Association for Computing Machinery.
- [97] TEKINBAS, K. S., AND ZIMMERMAN, E. *Rules of play: Game design fundamentals*. MIT press, 2003.
- [98] TELI, M., FOTH, M., SCIANNAMBLO, M., ANASTASIU, I., AND LYLE, P. Tales of institutioning and commoning: Participatory design processes with a strategic and tactical perspective. In *Proceedings of the 16th Participatory Design Conference 2020 - Participation(s) Otherwise - Volume 1* (New York, NY, USA, 2020), PDC '20, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 159–171.
- [99] TOBIAS, S., FLETCHER, J. D., AND WIND, A. P. Game-based learning. *Handbook of research on educational communications and technology* (2014), 485–503.
- [100] TYCHSEN, A., HITCHENS, M., BROLUND, T., AND KAVAKLI, M. Live action role-playing games: Control, communication, storytelling, and mmorpq similarities. *Games and Culture* 1, 3 (2006), 252–275.

- [101] TYGEL, A. F., AND KIRSCH, R. Contributions of paulo freire for a critical data literacy: A popular education approach. *The Journal of Community Informatics* 12, 3 (2016).
- [102] VERDEZOTO, N., BAGALKOT, N., AKBAR, S. Z., SHARMA, S., MACKINTOSH, N., HARRINGTON, D., AND GRIFFITHS, P. The invisible work of maintenance in community health: challenges and opportunities for digital health to support frontline health workers in karnataka, south india. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction* 5, CSCW1 (2021), 1–31.
- [103] VLACHOKYRIAKOS, V., CRIVELLARO, C., WRIGHT, P., AND OLIVIER, P. Infrastructuring the solidarity economy: Unpacking strategies and tactics in designing social innovation. In *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, 2018), CHI '18, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 1–12.
- [104] VON NEUMANN, J., AND MORGENSTERN, O. *Theory of Games and Economic Behavior*, 3rd ed. Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ, 1953.
- [105] WANG, C., AND HUANG, L. A systematic review of serious games for collaborative learning: Theoretical framework, game mechanic and efficiency assessment. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning* 16, 6 (2021).
- [106] WANG, H., SHEN, C., AND RITTERFELD, U. Enjoyment of digital games: What makes them “seriously” fun? In *Serious games*. Routledge, 2009, pp. 47–69.
- [107] WANG, T., AND HUANG, L.-Y. Viruscapse: A microscopic adventure game to guide conceptual learning of sars-cov-2 mechanisms. In *Extended Abstracts of the 2021 Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play* (New York, NY, USA, 2021), CHI PLAY '21, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 209–215.
- [108] WHITBY, M. A., IACOVIDES, I., AND DETERDING, S. “conversations with pigeons”: Capturing players’ lived experience of perspective challenging games. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 7, CHI PLAY (Oct. 2023).
- [109] WIDDER, D. G., DABBISH, L., HERBSLEB, J. D., AND MARTELARO, N. Power and play: Investigating “license to critique” in teams’ ai ethics discussions. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 8, CSCW2 (Nov. 2024).
- [110] WOUTERS, P., VAN NIMWEGEN, C., VAN OOSTENDORP, H., AND VAN DER SPEK, E. D. A meta-analysis of the cognitive and motivational effects of serious games. *Journal of educational psychology* 105, 2 (2013), 249.
- [111] ZAMBON, T., AMADORI, E., BERNARDELLI, P., AND PRANDI, C. Gameon! residency: Promoting peace, inclusivity, and sustainability through serious games. In *Proceedings of the 2024 International Conference on Information Technology for Social Good* (2024), pp. 462–466.

A External links

The website of Datopolis is <https://datopolis.theodi.org/>, while the GitHub repository can be accessed at <https://github.com/opendatateam/datopolis>.

B Game resources and rules

This section explains how the game resources guide the three outcomes in a typical play, as foregrounded by Figure 2.

B.1 Tools, tiles and tokens.

The game resources used for the **Tools** outcome are **data tiles**, **tool cards** and **tokens**. There are 78 **data tiles** representing 6 different types of data grouped into 3 domains. Transport and product data belong to the economic domain, health and democratic data belong to the social domain and geospatial and weather data belong to the environmental domain. Out of the 68 total **data tiles**, 66 have two sides: an open and a closed side. The rest of 12 **data tiles** only have one private side. Each tool card, from the total of 63 tool cards, describes one tool e.g. a mobile application containing a map with local public clinics, and visualises the number, type, combination and unique placement of data tiles needed to build that tool. A total of 100 tokens of different colours correspond to the players and are equally divided among them.

As instructed by tool cards which they draw by taking turns, players build tools by combining multiple data tiles. To match the tile combination from the tool card, players place data tiles on the table, by connecting them to existing ones. Once a data tile is placed, its position stays fixed for the remaining duration of the play. Upon placing the tile, the player decides whether to place it on an open or closed side and then places a token on it to claim ownership. An open tile can be used by any player at the table to build tools with, however a closed data tile can only be used by the player

who placed it on the table. If a player decides to use a private data tile, that tile will remain closed during the entire play. If a player needs to build a tool by combining open and closed tiles, they must negotiate with the player(s) who own(s) the closed tile(s) to share it (or them), thus turn it (or them) open side up. Any player can decide to open or close their data tiles, unless the tile is private, at any point during the game, but closing a data tile with multiple tools already built will cancel the tools all players have already built on it. Once all tiles needed to build a tool are positioned, the player takes ownership of the tool by placing one token on all data tiles used to build that tool. Although data tiles will have towers consisting of multiple tokens of different colours on top, as several tools have been built by multiple players, the first token at the base of the tower placed on each data tile represents the owner of that tile. The first player who has placed 10 tokens to claim their data tiles and their tools wins and thus the play stops.

B.2 Roles.

The only game resources added in the **Roles** outcome are **role cards**. The role cards are assigned randomly to each player, and they must be kept secret during the entire gameplay. Each of the nine role cards describes a different role that fits into the private sector, public sector or third sector. Because each sector is guided by a different agenda, the assigned role influences the game play. For example, a scientist from the public sector is driven by the agenda of long-term sustainability, and should encourage the availability of environmental data. Consequently, the player with this role wins if, at the moment when the play is stopped, all environmental data tiles are open. Throughout the game, the players must prioritise the tools and data tiles that fit their agenda in the way they develop tools and negotiate with other players to open data tiles. Winning by fulfilling a role is only revealed once another player has stopped the game after building on 10 data tiles, by revealing the **role card**. This type of play allows for multiple winners.

B.3 Events, town dashboard and markers.

The game resources added for the **Events** outcome are **event cards**, **town dashboard** and **dashboard markers**. The 39 event cards each describe one type of event that disturbs the town's wellbeing. Each player draws an event card at the end of their turn and based on it, they update the **town dashboard**. The **town dashboard** visually represents the town score on the social, economic and environmental domains, which is typically lowered by **event cards**, and increased by new tools developed or by player actions according to roles. The tools can increase the 3 domains according to the domain symbols represented on their corresponding tool cards. The **3 dashboard markers** indicate the score on each domain up to date, is placed at zero, which is in the middle of the dashboard, at the beginning of the game and is moved by each player after their turn ends. Once the markers on all 3 domains are at a maximum, all players win or they lose, if the markers are all 3 at a minimum, thus the game stops.

C Data collection protocol

The data collection protocol can be found on this Miro board https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVLMvxFY=?share_link_id=813046605488.